

Regional Integration and Trade in Africa

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to examine the potential for intra-Africa trade and the effect of regional economic integration on economic development through such trade. In Africa, the intra-regional trade is less as compared to the other trading blocks of Asia and Europe. The study finds out the main factors of low intra-regional trade by selecting four major economic communities in Africa namely COMESA, ECOWAS, IGAD, and SADC. The study applied the traditional gravity model of Anderson-van Wincoop in panel data. The gravity model variables are Gross Domestic Product GDP, bilateral real exchange rate, population, common language, common colonizer and distance. These variables are found to be very important factors for regional trade flows in Africa. The result shows that REC's impact on the bilateral trade. ECOWAS and SADC have a significant impact and have increased the bilateral trade among their countries members, COMESA has an insignificant coefficient impact on bilateral trade between the member's states and IGAD also has an insignificant but positive coefficient impact on the regional trade integration flows.

Keywords: Regional Integration Trade, Economic Integration, Gravity Model, Africa

1. Introduction

Africa ranks near the bottom when it comes to competing in the global economy, held back by fragmented markets that inhibit efficiency and constrain economic growth. Now a new player is emerging with the potential to defragment Africa and boost the productivity of its economies: the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA). In March 2018, 44 African heads of state signed a framework to establish a single continental market for goods and services, with free movement of capital and business travelers. Five additional countries, including South Africa, joined in July (Laursen, 2018). The AfCFTA still needs ratification by the parliaments of at least 22 countries; seven have done so thus far (De Melo & Tsikata, 2015). In addition to increasing market efficiency and reducing the cost of doing business by offering opportunities for economies of scale, the AfCFTA could ease trade and investment flows and shift the composition and direction of foreign direct investment flow into Africa. The Global Competitiveness Index, a performance indicator generated every year by the World Economic Forum to benchmark countries, shows large variations in national competitiveness rankings. These have to do with the stage of economic development, the gap in physical and technological infrastructure between developed and many developing economies and the inability of a number of developing economies to undertake the critical economic and institutional reforms needed to raise their market efficiency (Geda & Seid, 2015).

The few African countries that have emerged as the fastest-growing economies in the past decade have also been on an upward trajectory on the global competitiveness ladder. Increasingly, these countries (most notably Côte d'Ivoire, Ethiopia, and Rwanda) are drawing on their improving competitiveness and macroeconomic environment to diversify their sources of growth and trade and, in the process, expand their share of the global market pie (Thow et al., 2015). However, most African countries are probably latecomers in the race to boost competitiveness. Lately, the global economic environment has been dominated by the rise of beggar-thy-neighbor nationalism and creeping protectionism (Oseni & Pollitt, 2016). Leading economies are moving away from the rules-based system that has governed global trading arrangements for decades toward a new mercantilist system that measures a country's economic performance by its trade surplus. In this new reality, competitiveness is perhaps even more important for emerging market and developing economies. In

Africa, the push to deepen economic integration and boost intra-African trade under the AfCFTA is also likely to mitigate the costs of adverse global shocks. A larger effective domestic market acts as insurance against disruptions to global trade associated either with global volatility or with contraction in global demand.

The economies of African countries particularly that of the Sub-Saharan are divided, and the landmass, in general, has been minimized in the worldwide market. The joined (GDP) of Sub Saharan Africa was USD 378.6 billion in 2014 compared to the GDP of the Netherlands which was USD 396 billion. The worldwide offer of stock fare of Sub-Saharan Africa in 2014 was 2.6 percent which expanded just to 3.7 percent in 2014 in contrast with that of South Eastern Asia which was around 8.9 percent in 2012. As far as population, there were around 20 countries with a population of 6 million or less in 2010. Such little and divided local markets don't bolster a substantial number of firms (Shuaibu, 2015). So policy creators, pioneers and different partners in Africa have since called for joint action towards regional trade by leveraging on economies of scale and extended intra-regional trade through industrialization and better development policies. Subsequently, numerous local monetary networks had jumped up in the mainland especially since the 1960s when most African countries got autonomy (Chenaf-Nicet, D., & Rougier, E. 2016).

Africa's regional integration is not remarkable. The vast number of RIAs has done little to advance intra-regional trade. That brings up issues about the suitability of this straight measures for trade and the difficulties implementing them. The particular factors that have brought about Africa's and sub-Saharan Africa's, generally baffling financial performance in the course of recent decades have been the focal point of many inquiries. Dependence on not many fare products essential items speaking to in excess of 80 percent of Africa's complete fares in late 10 years and a couple of divisions are a piece of this story. Such high reliance on products makes extreme limitations on development because of ware value unpredictability, a factor which is outside to these nations and past the extent of their local approaches (Carranza, 2017). In spite of this acknowledgment, numerous African countries do not have the modern limit with regards to broadened fabricated products and are looked with the deficient foundation to help regional trade. Despite the fact that sub-Saharan Africa is one of the quickest developing areas on the planet at present this development shows to be naturally delicate and dependent on mutilated factors as opposed to sound economic fundamentals. Thus, it has been generally accepted that an adjustment in trade, combined with industrialization, an improvement in the framework, and basic change, would be key procedures in activating reasonable development ways in sub-Saharan Africa (Dihel & Goswami, 2016).

2. Theoretical Perspective and Literature Review

The gravity model has had reliable experimental accomplishment for analysis in numerous area, for example, moving, driving, the travel industry, foreign direct investment, and two-sided trade integration flows (Yotov, Y. V., et al., 2016; Tumwebaze & Ijjo, 2015). Despite the fact that the model had such observational accomplishment for long, it was questioned and criticized for the absence of theoretical elements. Following this analysis, exchange financial analysts had endeavored to figure the theoretical legitimizations dependent on various establishments. The Ricardian theory and Heckscher-Ohlin were the trade integration and investments assumptions which were utilized as clarification for global trade designs (Pietrangeli, 2016).

(Wu et al., 2017) build up a theoretically grounded admirable gravity model which owes its structure to homothetic leanings approximated by consistent versatility of substitution utility capacity for customers. Buyers' utilities increment from devouring to a greater extent a specific decent, or from expending a variety of merchandise. On the generation side, Anderson-van Wincoop display expects that each firm delivers a novel item under expanding comes back to scale. Subsequently, buyers appreciate a group of items from various countries. He further demonstrates is that it considers the multilateral trade obstacle. Obviously, the instinct behind multilateral opposition is that the more protection from trade all others an area is, the more it trade with a given respective partner.

It has been explained by (Bankole, Osei-Bryson, & Brown, 2015) who originally attempted to give theoretical security to gravity model reliant on steady versatility of substitution feelings and products that are separated by

country of a starting point which came to be known as the Armington assumption. The implications of these suppositions are that countries devour probably a portion of each great from each country regardless of what the costs are. Subsequently, in balance, all countries participate in global trade integration, and all items are traded with the goal that nationwide pay is the total of home and outside interest for the ware that every country yields. Thus bigger countries will in general export more and import more.

According to (Muntschick, 2016) the gravity model under the suspicion of expanding comes back to scale to the foundation. He further figures the theoretical clarification for the gravity model dependent on the Heckscher-Ohlin beliefs of factor blessing. (Mayer & Thoenig, 2016) build up a Ricardian model of international trade integration dependent on the distinction in innovation that combines physical elements. He gives straightforward delivery that relates respective trade volumes to deviations from obtaining power equality and to improve and geographic obstructions.

Te Velde, D. W. (2017) analyzes diverse determinations of the gravity model of trade. They additionally inspect the effect of the local mix on trade volumes by taking five local trading alliances. The authors connected diverse details pooled cross-area display, and fixed impacts show. They discovered that the impact of European trade integration on trade volume is humble. The outcome from the fixed impact show proposes that the trading integration had a significant impact on foreign direct investment (Achiume, T. E., & Landau, L. B. 2015).

Giovannetti, G., & Sanfilippo, M. (2016) apply the conventional gravity model to inspect the trading capability of Sub-Saharan Africa. Despite the fact that the intra-Sub Saharan Africa trade is low, he further demonstrates that genuine intra-regional is higher than the potential as the evaluated outcome from the gravity show uncovers. Bende-Nabende, A. (2017) investigated the determinants of trade flows and integration on intra-local trade potential in Sub-Saharan Africa, and the grouping of intra-regional trade. The outcome shows that cross border trade represents the bigger offer of intra-regional trade. Separation likewise gives off an impression of being the factor behind the centralization of respective trade between nations in the landmass.

Schwindenhammer, S. (2016) examines determinants of two-sided trade flows and internal loads of foreign direct investment applying the gravity model approach in a board informational index up. Using customary gravity model factors, he incorporates factors to control for the effect of provincial monetary networks on trade and FDI inflows.

Nyanzi, J. B., Babyenda, P., & Bbale, J. M. (2016) investigations the effect of regional trade agreements on intra-exchange selected agro-sustenance items in three integrated regional communities which are COMESA, EAC, and SADC. The examination finds that geographic parting impacts the intra-regional trade adversely; though the gross domestic product GDP of these countries have the normal positive signs. Other than the conventional determinants of respective trade the author discovers positive and huge coefficients for the regional trade flows which suggest that these trading blocs as well as intra-regional trade in the items. According to Moon, W. (2017) researches the halfway and general harmony effects of major regional trade understandings in Africa applying the gravity model approach. He finds that African financial mix understandings don't pursue the established financial theory assumption that trade flows will increment when trade barriers are decreased. Except for AMU, all RECs incorporated into the investigation have measurably noteworthy negative effects on trade exchange flows among individuals.

3. Techniques for estimation and Data Source

For data estimation techniques and data sources gravity model has been used in international studies of trade Tinbergen (1962; Florensa, L. M., et al., 2015). This model used for prediction bilateral trade export and import among countries gross national product as well as the geographical distance between them. The gross national product is associated with the country export supply and importing country's gross national product specifies total demand for consumption. Geographical distance is associated with the transport costs (Anyanwu, J. C., & Yaméogo, N. D. 2015). As per gravity model when regional trade trends enhance the country's gross national product importing and exporting is also increased. If the geographic distance between the trading partners increases. Mathematically the traditional gravity model is expressed as:

$$T_{ij} = aY_i^{\beta_1} Y_j^{\beta_2} D_{ij}^{\beta_3} \eta_{ij} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$Y_{i(j)}$ is indicating the gross national product of countries, where D_{ij} is an indication of the geographical distance between countries and a, b are indicating the parameter. η_{ij} denoted the error which is assumed to be independent of the repressors.

Traditional gravity model including the remoteness proxy

$$T_{ij} = aY_i^{\beta_1} Y_j^{\beta_2} D_{ij}^{\beta_3} N_i^{\beta_4} N_j^{\beta_5} RTA_{ij}^{\beta_6} A_{ij}^{\beta_7} REM_{it}^{\beta_8} REM_{jt}^{\beta_9} \eta_{ij} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\ln T_{ij} = \ln \alpha + \beta_1 \ln Y_i + \beta_2 \ln Y_j + \beta_3 \ln D_{ij} + \beta_4 \ln(N_i) + \beta_5 \ln(N_j) + \beta_6 RTA_{ij} + \beta_7 A_{ij} + \beta_8 \ln REM_i + \beta_9 \ln REM_j + \ln \eta_{ij} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$\ln T_{ijt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 d_t + \beta_2 d_{it} + \beta_3 d_{jt} + \beta_4 \ln D_{ij} + \beta_5 t_{ijt} + \beta_6 C_{ijt} + U_{ijt} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

4. Results

The results are based on the estimation which has been taken from different sources. For the purpose of this study, we collected data for the dependent variables and bilateral trade for different countries from the International Monetary Fund’s (IMF) and Trade Statistics Direction. The date covered 48 African countries between 2009 and 2018 and consisted of 60,736 data points. Some of the trade points are missing due to error. The gross domestic product GDP’s, Per Capita Income and the current population have been selected from the World Development Indicators database. There are also some other dummy variables has been used and collected from the database of CEPII. The author Mayer and Zignago (2005) has developed a distance variable by using a formula based on the latitude and longitude from the capital cities. Whereas the proxy for the multilateral trade resistance, i.e., REM_{it} is own computation following (Were, M. 2015). Bilateral real effective exchange rate, RER_{ijt} , which is the ratio of exporter’s real exchange rate to importer’s real exchange rate is also our own computation using (Kassim, L. 2015) real effective exchange rate data.

Detail of description data is following;

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics Results

Variable Details		Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max	Obsns.
Exports	Overall	9.9	71.55	0.0	2809	N= 35600
(Million USD)	Between		61.14	0.0	1121	n=2020
	Within		43.33	-700.2	2333	T= 18
GDP (Million USD)	Overall	19738.2	45736.28	80.2	363704	N= 836
	Between		34414.40	131.6	191499	n = 47
	Within		18386.95	-62841.8	189761	T = 18
GDP per Capita	Overall	1393.7	2495.13	69.1	28103	N =836
	Between		2061.90	131.4	8561	n = 47
	Within		1432.00	-6124.2	21691	T = 18
Population (Mn)	Overall	17.5	23.86	0.1	158	N =864
	Between		23.82	0.1	130	n = 48
Bilateral Exch. Rate	Overall	1.1	0.52	0.1	12	N=36720
	Between		0.35	0.5	5	n=2070
	Within		0.39	-2.6	8	T = 18
Adjacency		0.09	0.39	0	1	N=2256
Common Language		0.50	0.60	0	1	N =2256
Common Colonial		0.30	0.50	0	1	N =2256

Interpretation of Results and Discussions

The traditional gravity model estimation has been shown in the table no 1 below; which indicated that estimation from the Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood. The results revealed that traditional gravity model variables are positive and significant importance of bilateral trade flows in Africa. The exporters and importers income considered or measured by gross domestic product GDP had significant impacts on the trade flows and integration. So PPML gives statistically positive and significant effects of coefficients for the gross domestic product (GDP).

Table 2
The Intuitive Gravity Model Result

Technique of Estimation	PPML	
Variables Names	Coefficient	Standard Error
Exporters GDP	2.726***	(0.0362)
Importers GDP)	0.362***	(0.0352)
Common Language (Dummy)	0.140	(0.145)
Common Colonizer (Dummy)	1.022***	(0.139)
Distance	-1.272***	(0.131)
IGAD	00.44	(0.582)
COMESA	-0.156***	(0.0165)
SADC	0.352***	(0.0298)
ECOWAS	3.782***	(0.224)
Per Capita Difference	-0.00052	(0.00297)
Ln Importers Area	-0.476***	(0.041)
Ln Exporters Area	-0.253***	(0.0454)
Bilateral Enhance Rate	0.0577***	(0.00562)
Ln Exporter Population	-0.0623	(0.0464)
Ln Importer Population	0.986***	(0.0441)
Ln (Remoteness) Importers	0.409***	(0.0118)
Ln (Remoteness) Exporters	0.323***	(0.0124)
Constant	-42.39***	-1.265
Observations	35,361	
Number of Paired	2,621	

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table 2 shows that bilateral trade costs of all dummy variables which are consisted of geographical distance, common language, and common colonizer. According to the results and theory of previous researchers geographical distance has bilateral trade impact in Africa regional trade with the coefficient estimation from the PPML results is negative but significantly. As per result of Pseudo, Poisson Maximum Likelihood estimation technique indicates that elasticity of trade to distance is -1.272 which 12 % increase the distance reduces among African countries as well as African trade integration. The second dummy variable common language has a significant and positive effect with the coefficient of 0.140 which indicate that if the language is common and the same for a pair of countries, it will enhance the 14 percent trade flows. The third dummy variable which is associated with the historical and cultural indicator common colonizer which also has a significant impact on the trade flows and reducing the transaction costs to encourage bilateral trade in Africa. The results are also revealed that ECOWAS and SADC created the trade between the members and have a positive and significant impact with the coefficient estimation value of 0.352, but dummy variable IGAD has insignificant between

COMESA with the coefficient estimation value of -0.156.

Table 3
Anderson-van Wincoop Gravity Model Results

Technique of Estimation	PPML	
Variables Names	Coefficient	Standard Error
Common Language (Dummy)	0.582***	(0.162)
Common Colonizer (Dummy)	0.672***	(0.152)
Ln Distance	-1.627***	(0.172)
IGAD	1.651***	(0.621)
COMESA	-0.0309	(0.0352)
SADC	0.193***	(0.0621)
ECOWAS	0.292	(0.341)
Ln Per capita Difference	-0.0816***	(0.00526)
Bilateral Exchange rate	0.776***	(0.0452)
Exporter Fixed Effects	Yes	---
Importer Fixed Effect	Yes	---
Year Fixed Effects	Yes	---
Constant	-24.36	(35.21)
Observations	34,521	

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Above table 3 shows that the estimation result of the augmented gravity model which has been discussed the year, exporter and importers fixed effects over the time to control the multilateral trade in Africa. The results output revealed that common language and common colonizer is playing a significant role in the bilateral trade integration and geographical distance also has a positive impact on the bilateral trade. The first dummy variable common language has a positive and significant impact with the coefficient value of 52 percent on the bilateral trade whereas common colonizer also has a positive impact with the coefficient estimation of 67 percent on bilateral trade in Africa. The other variables of the dummy which included the COMESA, IGAD, ECOWAS and SADC also have a positive and significant impact on the bilateral trade flows in Africa. The results show that COMESA coefficient estimation found to be insignificant suggesting that this REC is weak in facilitating bilateral trade among member states which is consistent with the findings by Pietrangeli, Giulia. (2016), Were, M. (2015), and De Melo, Jaime, & Tsikata, Yvonne. (2015). IGAD and SADC, on the other hand, have created trade among member states.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this paper is to investigate the regional integration and trade in Africa. The paper discussed the Africa intra level is low when we compared it with the trading blocs in Europe and Asia and has remained marginalized in the global market. Excluding the informal cross border trade among many African countries, the formal intra-regional trade in the continent lingers around 10 to 12 percent of its global exports. The study covered the some factors of intra-regional trade in Africa and contributed the knowledge in regional trade integration and selected economic communities (ECOWAS, COMESA, SADC, and IGAD) with the help of theoretical gravity model. The output of the study is indicated that common language, common colonizer, GDP, distance is the most vital factors to enhance the bilateral trade flows in Africa. It is also shown that these all factors of bilateral trade affect the trade flows between partner's countries. Gross domestic GDP of the importing and exporting countries also has a positive and significant impact on the regional integration trade flows. Regional economic integrations are thought to promote bilateral trade and the growth by bringing fragmented economies into a single large market. The result from this paper implies that African countries

should invest much on physical infrastructure to link neighboring countries, harmonize trade policies, and simplify customs procedures so that the existing regional economic communities would promote intra-regional trade.

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